

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CLIL APPROACH IN ESP COURSES IN HIGHER EDUCATION OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The present article aims to look at the benefits of implementing Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) as a new approach in ESP courses in Uzbekistan Higher Education. Although there are numerous worldwide studies on the adoption of CLIL, relatively limited research has been done to explore its implementation in Uzbekistan Higher Education. Initially, the researcher explored the latest studies on the importance of CLIL in ESP courses and hypothesized that this approach was more likely to benefit ESP students in non-linguistic departments. The study involved an ESP instructor of Foreign Languages Department and 26 biology students of Science Department at Namangan State University. The purposes of the study was to find out the effectiveness of teaching language through CLIL pedagogy and clarify the attitudes towards its implementation from the students' perspectives. The two questionnaires were used to analyze the needs of the learners, their views and effects of language and content learning to enhance the biology students' professional communicative competence, content learning as well as their attitudes towards the implementation of CLIL approach. The findings revealed that the use of CLIL approach in ESP classes increased the students' motivation to learn both English and content, and the students in the experimental group felt more confident in their professional communicative competence. Thus, CLIL has positive implications on teaching ESP courses in non-linguistic faculties at universities although there are several challenges of its implementation in Higher Education in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Professional Communicative Competence, Biology students, language learning, Higher Education.

Introduction

It is crucial for future work candidates to establish professional, business, and social ties with foreign partners and colleagues, and converse with foreign specialists in the context of wide international connections with other nations. The acquisition of a strong command of the English language and the ability to communicate effectively in professional settings are vitally important in the competitive work market. Therefore, the demand for learning a foreign language for work-related reasons has consequently surged in higher education institutions in recent years. Higher education institutions offer foreign language instruction with the goal of helping students become proficient communicators and gain professional proficiency in the language so they can successfully pursue other professional endeavors.

In Uzbekistan context, the ministry of education has enforced policies targeted at teaching English as a foreign language starting from kindergartens. In addition, the Ministry of Higher Education has implemented the integration of English as the medium of instruction at universities. According to State Education Standards for Higher Education, English B2 levels are a requisite for students of non-linguistic majors. Undergraduate and postgraduate students are required to learn English in order to manage the academic discourse and knowledge of their disciplines.

One of the most innovative approaches to teach language and content simultaneously is Content and Language Integrated Learning, commonly known as CLIL. CLIL is a dual-focused educational pedagogy that integrates language learning and content learning at the same time (Coyle, Hood and Marsh, 2010). CLIL allow students to acquire a specific academic subject in the target language, usually English. Developed in 1990s, CLIL was used by educators and language instructors as a new approach to meet the changing needs of learners due to the historical, political and societal influences of the 1980s.

Dalton-Puffer (2011) views CLIL as "an educational approach where curricular content is taught through the medium of a foreign language, typically to students participating in some form of mainstream education at the primary, secondary, or tertiary level". In other words, this approach aims to develop students' proficiency in an additional language, while also learning subject-matter content. Building upon the definition and objectives of CLIL, the 4Cs curriculum (Coyle et al, 2010, p. 41) describes important components for a successful CLIL lesson:

- Content: Progression in knowledge, skills and understanding related to specific elements of a defined curriculum.
- Communication: Using language to learn while learning to use language.
- Cognition: Developing thinking skills which link concept formation (abstract and concrete), understanding, and language.
- Culture/community: Exposure to diverse perspectives and shared understandings, which deepen awareness of oneself and otherness.

Through the incorporation of these core components (language, content, culture/community, and cognition), CLIL instruction has the potential to enhance students' proficiency in foreign languages and subject-matter content. In addition, this approach aims to build and reinforce learners' knowledge of other disciplines while using the language to solve problems and develop critical thinking.

In Higher Education settings, where students have previously been taught ESP courses, CLIL programs have been established to attract international students and improve employability for domestic students (Costa and Coleman 2010). According to some experts, ESP is a specific type of CLIL, and both approaches improve language and content acquisition at the same time (Jendrych and Wisniewska 2010). Others, meanwhile, contend that there are notable distinctions. For example, while CLIL focuses on studying language and subject at the same time, ESP emphasizes the need to enhance language within a particular discipline. Additionally, according to Ruiz-Garrido and Fortanet-Gomez (2009), ESP courses are isolated, primarily focused on the language teacher and student, and designed to address language demands. Because contextual elements must be considered for the program to be successful, CLIL

engages a wider number of stakeholders, including discipline teachers and domain experts (Fernandez 2009; Jendrych & Wisniewska 2010; Ruiz-Garrido & Fortanet-Gomez 2009). Thus, it can be concluded that CLIL could be considered as a continuum of pedagogical approaches, which include ESP.

Method

The present research was conducted in a formal tertiary education setting, Namangan State University (NamSU) in Uzbekistan. ESP courses are taught in non-linguistic departments as a compulsory course during mainly first and second academic study year. In most non-linguistic departments ESP curricula used focuses on teaching academic English and sometimes subject matter topic inclusion due to the lack of experienced teachers and low level of students' language proficiency in English.

For the scope of this study, two questionnaires were designed. They were distributed to first-year twenty-six undergraduate students at the Department of Natural Science during the fall semester of the academic year 2021-2022, before the beginning and after completing the ESP course. The first questionnaire is divided into three sections; that is personal details section, their current English language use and their attitude and perspectives to learn English. This questionnaire is aimed to conduct at the beginning of the course. The second questionnaire is designed as the course evaluation by the students and their reflections towards to the implementation of CLIL approach in their ESP course. The students should not devote more than twenty minutes to fill in both questionnaires. The respondent is given a set of alternatives in the form of closed questions, mostly Yes/No and Likert scale type.

Findings and Discussion

Based on the information gathered from the first questionnaire, the students' profile was revealed. The overwhelming majority of students were male (18 out of 26 students) and most ranged between 18-20 years old. This was expected as the specific ESP course is taught in the first year of studies. In addition, as for language proficiency, more than half of the students thought to be themselves at B1 level and the others placed themselves at A2 level. Two students were certificate holders and both of them had previously attended other General English courses throughout their studies. Also, it can

be seen Diagram 1, the large proportion of learners need to learn English not only for just entertainment, travelling and obtaining language proficiency certificates, but also, most importantly, for their professional development. They admitted that they would have to read English materials, which could not be found in their first language in order to enrich their knowledge in their specialized field. Furthermore, most of them planned to do research in their area, write and publish articles in foreign outlets. Based on the findings, the course curriculum was designed and CLIL approach was implemented throughout the course for the fall semester.

Diagram 1.

Diagram 1. Students` needs in learning English

The second questionnaire was conducted after completing the course and it explored the students' attitudes and perceptions towards CLIL instructional strategies implemented in the ESP course, attitudes and perceptions towards possible full CLIL implementation across the curriculum.

The overall data summary showed that students preferred CLIL's dual focus, which integrates language and content. Overall, the respondents felt that language and content knowledge development benefited from the integration of content linked to other curriculum disciplines. Thus, in university contexts, CLIL aims to support learners' academic development as well as their achievement of academic language

competency (Naves 2009). Additionally, it was clear that students preferred the use of CLIL techniques and procedures. The vast majority of students felt comfortable working on assignments requiring active involvement, teamwork, and research skills, and they valued the more interactive aspect of learner-centered activities (Ruis-Garrido & Fortanet-Gomez 2009). According to other research, CLIL techniques and procedures gave students a variety of chances to exchange ideas and knowledge through social interaction (Pistorio 2010), which helped them build their social, group, and overall cooperative learning skills. The findings showed that students' confidence in their language and topic knowledge had grown, and they felt at ease with CLIL activities and processes (Wiesemes 2009). Furthermore, students had a strong desire to acquire the target language, maybe as a result of seeing its use in everyday situations and the fact that it was useful. The most significant finding, however, is that most students preferred a medium level of CLIL exposure more than a totally dual approach or full curriculum application of CLIL. Given students' preference for collaborative work, certain activities, assignments, or projects could be coordinated by both language and content teachers (Ruis-Garrido & Fortanet-Gomez 2009), as experts suggest that CLIL programs require a collaborative effort from all members involved (Naves 2009). As Carloni (2010) indicates CLIL involves thorough methodological planning and this should be brought to the attention of the content teachers, otherwise the quality of teaching and learning will not reach the objectives.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the participants' responses to the questionnaire items have led to important conclusions regarding CLIL implementation in Higher Education. The findings revealed that the use of CLIL approach in ESP classes increased the students' motivation to learn both English and content, and the students in the experimental group felt more confident in their professional communicative competence than their counterparts in the control group. Thus, CLIL has positive implications on teaching ESP courses in non-linguistic faculties at universities although there are several challenges of its implementation in Higher Education in Uzbekistan.

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